

THE PROBLEM OF FAKE NEWS IN INDIA: ISSUES, CONCERNS AND REGULATION

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Abstract:

In India, fake news refers to disinformation or misinformation spread by word of mouth and traditional media, as well as more recently through digital means, including edited videos, memes, unverified advertisements, and social media propagated rumours.

Throughout the country, fake news spread through social media has become a severe problem, potentially triggering mob violence. At least 20 people were killed due to misinformation passed around on social media in 2018.

The number of social media users in India is the largest globally across platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, WhatsApp, ShareChat, and TikTok. Social media platforms have introduced many restrictions on sharing a post under pressure from government and regulators such as the Election Commission.

In India, fake news has more potential to cause damage due to the greater penetration of the internet, which has grown from 137 million internet users in 2012 to over 600 million now.

India is WhatsApp's largest market, with over 230 million users, and as a result, it is a powerful platform for disseminating false information. One of the main problems is that recipients tend to believe anything they receive over social media due to their lack of knowledge.

Key Words: Misinformation, Internet, Social media, propaganda

Definition of Fake News

While there is no universally accepted definition of the term “fake news”, the definition provided by the Ethical Journalism Network is thus far the most comprehensive. It defines fake news as "information that is likely to be perceived as news, which has been deliberately fabricated and is disseminated to deceive others into believing falsehoods or doubting verifiable facts".

From this definition, it is clear that in order to be characterized as 'fake news', the information received must: a) be false or fabricated b) created with the deliberate intention to deceive the recipient into believing falsehoods or into doubting verifiable facts, and finally c) look so credible in its presentation that it is indistinguishable from traditional news, thereby influencing the recipient's sense of trust positively.

Types of misinformation in India

Health Misinformation

"We're not just fighting an epidemic; we are fighting an infodemic" - WHO Director-General Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus

The rapid spreading of such misinformation primarily occurs through social media, resulting in the lack of adherence to recommended public health measures or engagement in non-recommended behaviours. One clear example of disseminated misinformation during the COVID-19 suggested that 5G cellular network towers contribute to the spread of the virus, reportedly causing people to attack network towers. With several similar cases of misinformation and fake news circulating and being shared on social media, tackling the COVID-19 'infodemic' has been established as a research priority in the WHO Response Strategy.

A Muslim man spreads coronavirus by licking fruits" may incite Hindus to stand against Muslim minorities.

Political Misinformation

Most of India's misinformation campaigns are created and run by political parties with highly sophisticated cyber-armies. Their propaganda uses domestic divisions and prejudices to attack political opponents and religious minorities. This targeted misinformation often has grave consequences, ranging from death threats to actual murders-in the past year, more than two dozen people were lynched in mobs sparked by nothing more than rumours circulated through WhatsApp.

Misinformation during Covid -19

False claims were also widely spread in India that eating vegetarian food and eliminating meat from your diet could prevent you getting coronavirus. The government launched campaigns to stop the spread of such misinformation.

These false WhatsApp messages and social media posts impacted both Muslim and non-Muslim groups alike who were involved in the meat industry. Poultry is one of the main forms of meat consumed in India." We were giving away chicken for free because we did not know what to do with the stock," said Sujit Prabhavle, a meat trader in the western state of Maharashtra." Our sales fell by 80%," he said.

"I saw a message on WhatsApp that said eating chicken would spread coronavirus, so people stopped buying meat," said Touhid Baraskar, another meat seller from Maharashtra.

Miscellaneous misinformation

This category includes a small number of misinformation mainly related to the military, technology, education, and economy. For example, "Tata Group of companies will not recruit JNU Student" and "Massive discovery of gold reserves" are economy-related, and "Mysterious apocalyptic planet spotted in the sky" is technology-related.

Laws and Regulation to Curb Fake News in India

There is no specific law against fake news in India. Free publication of news flows from Article 19 of the Constitution guarantees freedom of speech.

- Press Council of India, a regulatory body, can warn, admonish or censure the newspaper, the news agency, the editor or the journalist or disapprove the conduct of the editor or the journalist if it finds that a newspaper or a news agency has violated journalistic ethics.
- News Broadcasters Association (NBA) represents the private television news and current affairs broadcasters. The self-regulatory body probes complaints against electronic media.
- Indian Broadcast Foundation (IBF) also looks into the complaints against contents aired by channels.
- Broadcasting Content Complaint Council (BCCC) admits complaints against TV broadcasters for objectionable TV content and fake news.
- Indian Penal Code (IPC) has certain sections which could curb fake news: Sections 153 (wantonly giving provocation with intent to cause riot) and 295 (injuring or defiling place of worship with intent to insult the religion of any class) can be invoked to guard against fake news.
- Section 66 in The Information Technology Act, 2000: If any person, dishonestly or fraudulently, does any act referred to in section 43 (damage to the computer, computer system), he shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to three years or with a fine which may extend to five lakh rupees or both.
- Civil or Criminal Case for Defamation is another resort against fake news for individuals and groups hurt by the fake news. IPC Section 499 (defamation) and 500 (whoever defames another shall be punished with simple imprisonment for a term which may extend to two years, or with fine, or with both) provide for a defamation suit.

Factors contributing to the spread of misinformation in India

1. Low digital literacy More than 600 million Indians use the internet, but digital literacy and social media regulation are far behind.

"People get cheap internet-based tech on their smartphones, but they do not have the necessary education on how to assess the veracity of claims made in the messages," said Rajneil Kamath, a publisher at the Indian fact-checking portal NewscheckerIn.

2. The role of religion and media Religious divisions in India have also contributed to spreading false news online. As a result, disinformation targeting Muslims spiked after several members of an Islamic group who attended a religious gathering in Delhi tested positive for COVID-19.

3. Fact-checking cannot keep up The number of fact-checking organizations is often overwhelmed by the volume of fake news circulating.

The rapid spread of Fake News and disinformation online can have profound consequences.

Examples include:

- Distrust in the media
- Undermining the democratic process
- Platforms for harmful conspiracy theories and hate speech
- Spread of false or discredited science – e.g. anti-vax movement

Suggestions for combating fake news

Everyone has a responsibility to combat the scourge of fake news. The following steps may help to eliminate fake news effectively:

1. One of the most crucial things governments around the world can do is encourage independent, professional journalism. In a time of considerable turmoil, it is vital to have a healthy Fourth Estate independent of public authorities. The news industry should continue to focus on high-quality journalism that builds trust and attracts more significant audiences.

2. improving digital literacy among the general public

3. Technology firms should invest in technology to find fake news and identify it for users through algorithms and crowdsourcing.

4. In the online world, readers and viewers should be sceptical about news sources; news consumers have to keep their guard up and understand that not everything they read is accurate. Learning how to judge news sites and protect oneself from inaccurate information is a high priority in the digital age.

References

How to combat fake news and disinformation. <https://www.brookings.edu/research/how-to-combat-fake-news-and-disinformation/>

Al-Zaman, Md. Sayeed. (2021). Social Media Fake News in India. Asian Journal for Public Opinion Research. 9. 25-47. 10.15206/ajpor.2021.9.1.25.